

Eastern England SDE Safe Models, Safe AI: Governance and Disclosure Testing

Laura Clarke, Kshitij Nemade, Jack Adamson,
Alexis Joannides, Keiran Raine

March 2026

Contents

Authors	3
1. Executive summary	3
2. Project background	4
3. VISTA AI risk assessment toolkit.....	4
4. Model disclosure control using SACRO-ML.....	6
4.1. Deploying and testing SACRO-ML	6
4.2. Assessment of time and cost implications.....	6
5. Documentation	7
5.1. Supporting researchers	7
5.2. Supporting airlock managers	8
6. Audience and contributions.....	8
7. Impact.....	9
8. Feedback and process improvement	10
8.1. VISTA risk assessment toolkit feedback.....	10
8.2. SACRO-ML Feedback	11
8.3. EE-SDC process improvement	14
9. Conclusions and future direction.....	14
10. Acknowledgements.....	15
11. Glossary.....	15
12. References.....	17

Licence

This work © 2026 by HDR UK is licensed under

CC BY 4.0

Eastern England SDE – Safe Models, Safe AI: Governance and Disclosure Testing

VISTA SACRO-ML Workstream Final Report

Authors

Laura Clarke (Eastern England Secure Data Environment, Health Innovation East, ORCID: 0000-0002-5989-6898)

Kshitij Nemade (Eastern England Secure Data Environment, Health Innovation East, ORCID: 0009-0000-8670-0814)

Jack Adamson (Eastern England Secure Data Environment, Health Innovation East, ORCID: 0009-0003-9993-2544)

Alexis Joannides (Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust, University of Cambridge ORCID: 0000-0002-6618-256X)

Keiran Raine (Eastern England Secure Data Environment, Health Innovation East, ORCID: 0000-0002-5634-1539)

1. Executive summary

The SACRO-ML workstream sits at the heart of the Eastern England Secure Data Environment's¹ (EE-SDE) contribution to the VISTA Early Adopter programme. Its purpose was to establish and operationalise new tools and governance processes that enable Trusted Research Environments (TREs) to safely support machine-learning (ML) projects using sensitive health data. A central driver for this work was the opportunity to strengthen and enhance TRE capability in respect of ML projects. With demand from researchers increasing, TREs are now focusing on developing robust, evidence-based methods to assess the disclosure risks associated with exporting trained ML models.

This workstream developed the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit² to support TREs enabling projects that train ML models using sensitive data. The toolkit is designed to help TREs evaluate the suitability, feasibility and safety of ML projects from the earliest stages. It supports TREs to identify and mitigate privacy risks associated with model training and release, embedding structured governance aligned with the Five Safes framework³ and widely recognised guidance including RELEASE-AI⁴ and contributing to a more consistent national approach to AI oversight. A core component of the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit is the use of SACRO-ML⁵ to provide evidence-based model disclosure control before it can be egressed from a TRE.

Alongside the development of the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit, the team also tested SACRO-ML within the EE-SDE. Using representative ML workflows and a synthetic OMOP dataset, the team assessed the feasibility of SACRO-ML's two-stage approach: ante-hoc risk checking using the SafeModel wrapper, and

post-hoc empirical assessment through simulated attacks such as Likelihood Ratio and Worst-Case Membership Inference. This evaluation generated practical insight into how SACRO-ML performs under real analytical conditions and how researchers and airlock managers can integrate it into existing workflows.

Through this combined technical and governance work, the SACRO-ML workstream has significantly strengthened the EE-SDE's readiness to support secure, transparent and scalable AI research, while contributing valuable learning to the wider TRevolution community.

2. Project background

VISTA (Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI) is one of the DARE UK Early Adopter projects launched in January 2025. Led by Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust in partnership with Health Innovation East and Cambridge University Health Partners, VISTA is piloting TRevolution standards and AI capabilities within the EE-SDE.

The aims of VISTA were to support and enhance existing SDE processes. Demonstrating how large-scale AI-enabled research can be conducted safely, efficiently and consistently, whilst helping other TREs adopt these approaches. There were four specific aims:

- To complete a structured self-assessment against the SATRE benchmark specification and develop actionable recommendations to inform the next phase of TRE development
- Test and refine semi-automated research output checking in the EE-SDE
- Safely train and export ML and AI models from the TRE
- Support readiness for AI models to be deployed in NHS services

VISTA adopted three TRevolution capabilities: SATRE⁶ aligns the EE-SDE with a community driven specification adopted across UK TREs, now evolving to include federation and ML output control capabilities. SACRO⁷ enables more efficient and auditable disclosure checking by applying statistical disclosure control principles directly within analytical workflows. SACRO-ML extends this to ML models through ante-hoc and post-hoc risk assessments, including SafeModel evaluation and membership inference attack testing.

Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) was embedded through existing EE-SDE structures, including the Core Public Advisory Group (CPAG). This ensured that development of SATRE, SACRO and SACRO-ML reflected public expectations around transparency, accountability and appropriate use of automation.

This work package report focuses on insights from the EE-SDE work to support safely training and exporting outputs from AI and ML models as well as supporting AI model readiness for real-world deployment in NHS services.

3. VISTA AI risk assessment toolkit

The VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit provides TREs with a structured, evidence-based approach for assessing and managing the privacy risks that arise when training ML models on sensitive data. As TREs

increasingly receive AI-focused research proposals, they require consistent mechanisms to evaluate risk, determine feasibility, and apply appropriate safeguards. The toolkit addresses this need by offering a clear and practical process that aligns with established guidance including the Five Safes framework, RELEASE-AI, GRAIMATTER⁸ recommendations, and the ICO’s AI and Data Protection Risk Toolkit⁹.

The toolkit comprises four core components:

- **Researcher AI Questionnaire:** a structured questionnaire capturing proposed model types, data requirements, training approaches, and plans for model egress
- **A Structured AI Risk Assessment Form:** completed during feasibility review to evaluate disclosure risk and identify relevant controls
- **A Set of Actionable Controls:** a set of safeguards covering Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Data, Safe Settings and Safe Outputs, enabling TREs to proportionately manage risk throughout the ML lifecycle
- **A Released Trained Model Registry:** a record of all egressed models that supports transparency, auditability, and monitoring of secondary disclosure risks

A key capability embedded within the toolkit is the use of SACRO-ML. Our testing and deployment of this model disclosure control technology is described below in section 4. This technology is essential to provide TREs with evidence so they can make safe and defensible decisions about model egress and the required actionable controls associated with them.

The toolkit is designed for TRE operational teams; these include airlock managers, governance staff, and data access committees; it provides a workflow spanning data access request, feasibility assessment, training oversight, and project closure. The toolkit also incorporates patient and public insight gathered through the EE-SDE’s CPAG, ensuring the framework reflects expectations around transparency, accountability, and the responsible use of automation.

Figure 1. The project lifecycle stages and processes needed for each stage.

As ML methods and risks evolve, the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit is intended to remain adaptive; this first version establishes a foundation for consistent and trustworthy oversight of ML research within TREs and will continue to be refined in collaboration with the wider TRE community.

4. Model disclosure control using SACRO-ML

4.1. Deploying and testing SACRO-ML

To explore how ML model disclosure control could be operationalised within the EE-SDE we conducted a structured testing exercise using the SACRO-ML toolset. The aim was to understand how researchers and output checkers interact with SACRO-ML when preparing ML models trained on sensitive data, and to assess how effectively the tool supports privacy risk assessment prior to model release.

The first demonstrator use case focused on developing a Type 2 diabetes risk prediction model using a synthetic OMOP dataset¹⁰ derived from Synthea¹¹. A set of representative ML workflows were implemented, ranging from a baseline Random Forest model to more complex and tuned variants. This approach enabled us to evaluate SACRO-ML’s behaviour across different levels of modelling complexity.

For each workflow, models were trained within the EE-SDE’s Amazon Web Services based environment and then processed through SACRO-ML’s disclosure risk testing framework. After wrapping models in the SACRO-ML Target object, simulated privacy attacks, such as the Likelihood Ratio Attack (LiRA) and WorstCase Membership Inference Attack, were executed to estimate the likelihood of training record inference. This allowed us to observe SACRO-ML from both a researcher and output checker perspective and to better understand how model disclosure control can be integrated into routine governance processes.

A second demonstrator use case was also recruited to train a pressure ulcer risk prediction model. Due to evolving research objectives, the introduction of a new data pipeline, and extended governance and contracting processes, feedback is still pending. While this use case will complete outside the formal VISTA project timeline, we remain committed to providing results and ensuring that the SACRO-ML trial continues to generate value for the TREvolution community.

4.2. Assessment of time and cost implications

Testing of SACRO-ML also provided insights into the computational and financial requirements of machine learning disclosure risk assessment within the EE-SDE. All analysis were performed on an m6a.xlarge compute instance (4 vCPU, 16 GiB RAM) using a 2.5GB dataset and trained models of approximately 50MB.

Typical workflow runtimes and associated compute costs were as follows:

Workflow Stage	Typical Runtime	Estimated Cost per Run
Model training	~1 hour	~£0.15
Disclosure-risk checking (SafeModel attack execution and report generation)	30–60 minutes	£0.08 – £0.15
Complete analytical workflow (training + disclosure risk evaluation)	1.5 – 2 hours	£0.23 – £0.30

Table 1: Compute Time and Cost per Analytical Stage.

These estimates are based on the current instance cost of approximately £0.15 per hour, excluding storage and taxes. The results show that a complete model development and disclosure-risk assessment cycle can typically be completed within 1.5-2 hours of active compute time.

5. Documentation

5.1. Supporting researchers

To support researchers working with ML models in the EE-SDE, we have developed researcher-facing guidance¹² that outlines how disclosure risk should be managed during model development and preparation for release. Acknowledging that the individuals building and evaluating models in the EE-SDE are not always the same as those who completed the original Data Access Request (DAR) or the accompanying AI Researcher Questionnaire, the guidance is designed to provide the essential context that may not otherwise be known to them, particularly around the types of disclosure risks associated with ML training. All researchers working in the EE-SDE will have completed standard statistical disclosure control training, and specialised ML-focused disclosure control support will also be available. The documentation aims to offer clear and practical self-service instructions on using the SACRO-ML toolset as well as on assembling the necessary artefacts and contextual information for disclosure review, complementing any additional guidance provided by airlock managers or external training.

This guidance starts by introducing the practical use of the SafeModel component of SACRO-ML within a typical ML workflow. Researchers develop and evaluate models using their usual analytical tools and then apply SafeModel wrappers to perform structured safety checks on the trained model. These checks examine model configuration and behaviour for potential disclosure risks, such as unsafe parameter choices, structural properties that may increase information leakage, or indicators of overfitting. Once the researcher is satisfied with model performance and safety checks, the SafeModel workflow generates a structured artefact and checkfile report that can be submitted for disclosure review. This workflow reflects established approaches to safe model release, including structured disclosure checks and controlled output mechanisms designed for use within TREs.

The guidance then moves on to provide a broader explanation of how disclosure risk should be assessed when training ML models within the EE-SDE. It describes the two-stage SACRO-ML approach: ante-hoc checks performed during model development using SafeModel, and optional post-hoc evaluation using simulated attacks to estimate potential privacy risks. The guidance also outlines the minimum information researchers must provide when submitting a model for review, including the model artefact, supporting datasets, and contextual documentation describing the model's purpose and evaluation approach. To complement the written guidance, an example Jupyter notebook has been developed using a synthetic OMOP dataset. This notebook demonstrates an end-to-end workflow showing how a researcher can construct a modelling dataset, train a baseline ML model, apply the SACRO-ML SafeModel wrapper, generate structured artefacts for disclosure review, and optionally run simulated privacy attacks as a diagnostic check.

5.2. Supporting airlock managers

To support airlock managers reviewing machine-learning models within the EE-SDE, a dedicated guidance document¹³ was developed describing how disclosure risk should be assessed prior to model egress. This material provides practical instructions on using SACRO-ML attack-based evaluation within the output-checking workflow and outlines the steps required to review submitted model artefacts in a consistent and structured manner. The documentation aims to ensure that disclosure risk is assessed systematically, that required artefacts are complete and interpretable, and that release decisions are supported by clear and reproducible evidence. The guidance is further supported by step-by-step notebook examples to aid practical implementation.

The first section of the guidance defines the minimum artefact requirements that must be provided by researchers when submitting a model for review. At a minimum, this includes the trained model file, clearly labelled training and testing datasets, and a README or model card describing the model purpose, type, features used, outcome definition, and any preprocessing steps. This ensures that airlock managers have sufficient context to understand how the model was developed and to assess whether the submitted artefacts are complete and suitable for evaluation. Where required information is missing or unclear, airlock managers are expected to request clarification before proceeding with assessment.

The guidance then describes the end-to-end disclosure control workflow within the secure environment. Airlock managers create a clean checking notebook, validate the structure and consistency of the submitted data and model, and prepare the inputs required for SACRO-ML evaluation by wrapping them into a Target object. The SACRO-ML attack workflow is applied in a structured sequence, beginning with preliminary checks as an initial structural screening step to assess model structure, followed by WorstCaseAttack as the primary assessment of membership inference risk, and finally LiRAAttack (Likelihood Ratio Attack) as a more comprehensive and realistic privacy test where earlier checks do not indicate clearly unacceptable risk. This staged approach ensures that computational effort is used proportionately while still providing a robust assessment of disclosure risk.

The final section of the guidance provides detailed interpretation support for attack outputs, including key metrics such as AUC (area under the curve), Advantage, significance indicators, and subgroup risk measures such as PDIF (probability difference) or PDFI (probability difference for individuals). These metrics are linked to indicative thresholds to support consistent and transparent decision-making across reviewers. Based on this evidence, airlock managers are expected to make a structured decision to approve the model, approve it with documented caveats, or reject it and provide clear feedback to the researcher. This process ensures that model egress decisions are evidence-based, consistent across projects, and aligned with the EE-SDE's governance framework for safe and responsible data use.

6. Audience and contributions

This workstream was delivered collaboratively by airlock managers and research governance leads from the EE-SDE team, supported by contributions from the SACRO-ML developers and informed by feedback from external researchers. The primary audience for these outputs is TRE operational teams, particularly airlock managers and governance representatives responsible for reviewing data access applications and overseeing

the safe egress of data, code and machine-learning models. The materials may also be valuable to other members of the TRE community, including data controllers and researchers, by helping them understand the key considerations involved in managing disclosure risks and other privacy impacts when training or validating machine-learning models on sensitive data within a TRE.

7. Impact

The SACRO-ML workstream represents an important development in enhancing the EE-SDE's capability to enable ML research involving sensitive data. It has established both the technical foundations and the governance structures required for safe, transparent and reproducible model egress. By integrating SACRO-ML into the EE-SDE's disclosure-control toolkit, we have moved beyond conceptual discussions of AI safety within TREs and demonstrated how a practical, operational method for assessing disclosure risks in trained models can be implemented. This marks a significant step in the EE-SDEs ability to provide structured, evidence-based assurance for ML outputs, enabling us to support categories of projects that were previously considered high-risk or difficult to manage responsibly.

Through this workstream we have established a functioning, end-to-end governance pathway for ML projects through the development of the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit. This includes early-stage feasibility assessment, ante-hoc disclosure checking, post-hoc empirical testing and structured release decisions. We have also demonstrated SACRO-ML in analytical workflows with synthetic data, showing that disclosure control can be embedded directly within model development rather than being introduced solely at the point of egress. Alongside this, the workstream has delivered operational clarity for airlock managers through new guidance, processes and decision-making aids that increase the repeatability and defensibility of assessments. Finally, the work has generated clear evidence in relation to the compute needs and operational costs involved in running SACRO-ML, enabling TREs to plan realistically for the resources required to govern ML safely.

As a result, the EE-SDE can support ML projects that train models on sensitive data with structured and proportionate evaluation of disclosure risks. Researchers can design for privacy from the outset by using SafeModel ante-hoc checks to identify issues early, leading to fewer errors or omissions at the egress stage. Airlock managers have access to reliable, empirical evidence produced by SACRO-ML's attack framework, strengthening the transparency and defensibility of release decisions. The EE-SDE is also better positioned to meet emerging national expectations around AI governance, including RELEASE-AI, TREvolution guidance and future regulatory requirements.

The impact of this work extends beyond the EE-SDE. By demonstrating what a practical, end-to-end ML disclosure-control process looks like within a functioning TRE, this workstream lowers adoption barriers for other environments. The VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit provides a reusable governance model that can be adopted or adapted by other TREs, supporting greater national consistency in how ML risks are understood and managed. The demonstrator workflow and accompanying materials provide a template for TREs earlier in their journey, enabling them to pilot SACRO-ML using synthetic data and structured processes without starting from scratch. In addition, the operational insights generated through this work contribute

directly to the TRevolution programme, offering real-world evidence on usability, performance, costs and governance implications that will accelerate learning across the sector.

Taken together, the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit and the implementation of SACRO-ML mark an important milestone in the EE-SDE's evolution from supporting predominantly statistical outputs to enabling safe, privacy-preserving machine-learning research at scale. This workstream has transformed ML governance from an aspirational idea into an operational reality, strengthening the ability of both the EE-SDE and the wider TRE community to support responsible AI innovation that delivers public benefit while maintaining robust protection for individuals' privacy.

8. Feedback and process improvement

8.1. VISTA risk assessment toolkit feedback

The evaluation of the AI Researcher Questionnaire and AI Risk Assessment Form provided an initial set of insights into how these tools support ML-specific governance within the EE-SDE. As with the early SACRO-ML testing, feedback naturally separated into two viewpoints. Researchers reflected on how well the questionnaire enabled them to describe their modelling intentions, while airlock managers focused on the usefulness of the forms during feasibility assessment and risk scoring. Initial use of the tools by two projects is already demonstrating good alignment with established TRE governance, and where further refinement will be needed as more users engage with the toolkit.

Researchers reported that the questionnaire was helpful in prompting them to articulate the technical details of their planned approach, particularly around model architecture, data use and preprocessing. The structure supported them to outline their methodology in a way that aligns with TRE feasibility requirements. Researchers also observed that the form offered limited opportunities to describe the reasoning behind specific modelling decisions. As a result, important contextual information about design choices or trade-offs was sometimes omitted or placed separately in the DAR, making it more difficult for airlock managers to understand the proposal as a coherent whole. While a clear rationale does not change the underlying risk assessment, it enables reviewers to understand the plans in context and recognise when particular modelling choices are appropriate given the project's aims, constraints or dataset characteristics. Further consideration is therefore needed on how best to support researchers to provide this explanatory detail. This also needs to be presented effectively to the airlock manager, so they and others involved in project feasibility review, have enough context to assess risks accurately, potentially engaging in additional discussion with the researcher before completing the assessment for the Data Access Committee (DAC).

Airlock managers commented positively on the structure and ordering of the AI Risk Assessment Form, noting that it followed a workflow familiar from other TRE governance activities. However, they identified areas where the clarity and auditability of the form could be improved. One emerging theme was the blending of risks identified by researchers with risks identified independently during review. Presenting these in clearly separated sections would allow reviewers to distinguish areas of alignment with the researcher's assessment from instances where additional risks or alternative interpretations have been identified. A similar separation for corresponding mitigations would provide a clearer record of the shared and distinct responsibilities between researcher and reviewer. Reviewers also observed that a field to record the rationale for each risk rating would reduce ambiguity and support more consistent scoring across review teams.

There was also discussion regarding the appropriate granularity within the Low, Medium and High rating scale. Reviewers recognised the value of a simple three-level structure, particularly for DAC decision-making. At the same time, they noted that some ML-related risks sit between categories and may require more differentiation in future versions of the toolkit. This will become more important as the range of model types and research use-cases broadens.

Across both user groups, there was agreement that we could further enhance clarity around how the Researcher AI Questionnaire, the DAR and the Risk Assessment Form connect and work together. At present, information relevant to ML-related risk assessment may be spread across the AI Risk Assessment form and the DAR, which means reviewers often need to reconcile and cross-reference details manually. Providing clearer guidance on how these components are intended to work together or redesigning certain elements so that key content is easier to locate, could help streamline the process by reducing duplication and improving consistency. Any such changes, however, would need to be proportionate, acknowledging that TRE projects differ in complexity, and not all will require this degree of technical specificity. This consideration underpins the decision to maintain the questionnaire as a separate form. The challenge will be to strike an appropriate balance, ensuring reviewers have sufficient information to make accurate, well-supported assessments, while avoiding unnecessary additional burden for researchers whose projects no warrant this degree of detail.

This feedback should be seen as an early indication of strengths and areas for improvement rather than a comprehensive evaluation. Continued testing across a broader range of model types and user groups will be essential to fully mature the tools. Nonetheless, the initial findings suggest that the toolkit provides a solid foundation for capturing relevant ML information and structuring risk assessment. At the same time, the feedback highlights the value of clearer separation of perspectives, improved justification fields and careful consideration of future risk-rating refinement. Enhancing these aspects will help ensure the tools support consistent, transparent and confident decision-making as TREs expand their capability to govern ML research.

8.2. SACRO-ML Feedback

The SACRO-ML testing exercise generated a clear set of insights into how the toolset supports ML disclosure control across the full EE-SDE workflow. Feedback separated naturally into two perspectives. Researchers focused on the experience of onboarding and model development, while airlock managers concentrated on the later stages of disclosure review and egress. Taken together, these observations show where current processes already align with established practice and where additional guidance or validation would improve consistency.

Researchers reported that the core tasks of data preparation, model training, and model evaluation remained consistent with standard ML practice. Integrating SACRO-ML did not fundamentally alter how models were developed. The challenges encountered were instead linked to practical workflow issues. These issues often emerged late in the workflow when researchers began preparing model artefacts for disclosure testing, which sometimes resulted in repeated work that could have been avoided. Providing guidance notebooks and pre-flight checks built into the system may help avoid these errors and reduce the need for re-work.

Several improvements were identified for platform integration within the TRE environment. Providing clear environment setup guidance specific to SACRO-ML could help ensure consistent installation and

configuration across projects. Additional practical guidance may also enhance usability by supporting users in selecting appropriate attack types for different model classes and data scenarios, and in interpreting results consistently within a disclosure control context. Long running attack processes would benefit from improved execution monitoring, including progress indicators and structured logging, together with support for checkpointing or restart, which would reduce the impact of interrupted runs when working with larger datasets.

A notable finding from the exercise was the importance of improving pre-flight validation checks. Many early errors stemmed from mismatched feature arrays, inconsistent feature ordering, or models saved in formats that were incompatible with the expected disclosure checking process. Automated validation at the point of model submission would help researchers identify these issues earlier. This could reduce unnecessary compute consumption and significantly improve the likelihood of successful first-time execution. This need becomes even more important as dataset sizes increase. Runtime analysis showed that SafeModel processing scales upward with training set size (Figure 2), largely because the generation of k-anonymity partitions becomes more computationally intensive. Although compute demands remained manageable within the test environment, they have the potential to prolong iterative development. Researchers therefore recommended an optional light version of SafeModel for experimentation, while keeping the full assessment for the final release stage.

A recurring insight was the opportunity to strengthen and refine the onboarding materials to better support users from the outset. Without simple worked examples, researchers required additional time to understand how SACRO-ML components fit into the modelling lifecycle. They consistently highlighted example notebooks, end-to-end demonstrations, and step-by-step guidance as particularly valuable for learning how to package model artefacts correctly and how to use the SACRO-ML tools at the appropriate stages. The EE-SDE team has incorporated these elements into our documentation, and SACRO-ML has released updated materials via the <https://sacro-ml.sacro-tools.org/> website. Both sets of documentation will benefit from further refinement as they are tested by a broader user community, and continuous improvement will be guided by feedback from wider use in live projects. Given that modern Python libraries have made training ML models significantly more accessible, it is important that the documentation supports users efficiently and does not create a higher barrier to participation than necessary for effective disclosure control.

To ensure SACRO-ML and model disclosure are widely understood and adopted, their integration into established and trusted standards and workflows is essential. Positioning them as optional but aligned components within existing frameworks, such as the ONS Safe Researcher Training¹⁴ and the Safe Data Access Professionals Network's Handbook on Statistical Disclosure Control for Outputs¹⁵ would support broader recognition, operational consistency and long-term sustainability.

Airlock managers responded positively to the structure and consistency of the automated SACRO-ML reports. The reports reliably captured key metadata including attack parameters, model identifiers, and summary metrics. This supported reproducible review and reduced the level of manual reconstruction required for assessments. At the same time, they noted that some disclosure risk metrics produced by the attack framework require clearer interpretive context. Terms such as PDIF ranges, FMAX (maximum F1 score values), and p-value thresholds were understood to be technically valid but not always intuitive for decision

making. Additional interpretive guidance, including worked examples and clear routes for peer and subject matter expert support, would help airlock managers reach consistent conclusions during disclosure review.

Figure 2: Comparison of Baseline Model and SafeModel Wrapper across increasing dataset sizes, showing substantial increases in computation time (CPU and wall time) for SafeModel while memory usage grows moderately for both. Time taken to train a model, SACRO-ML SafeModel vs standard process in seconds for different input record sizes, 5,000 to 20,000.

Overall, the testing exercise showed that SACRO-ML provides a strong foundation for ML disclosure control within the EE-SDE. Both researchers and airlock managers valued structured workflows, consistent artefact requirements, and robust automated reporting. The feedback also highlighted the importance of enhanced onboarding materials, clearer interpretive support, stronger platform integration guidance, execution monitoring and restart capabilities for long running jobs, and more comprehensive pre-flight validation. These

improvements would help ensure that disclosure risk assessment is smoothly integrated throughout the full modelling lifecycle, from the earliest stages of onboarding through to final model egress.

8.3. EE-SDC process improvement

Our second demonstrator project was unable to generate feedback within the VISTA project timeline due to several factors, including extended data approval process, delays in data delivery and unavoidable last-minute constraints on researcher availability. The EE-SDE team recognises that engaging researchers earlier using a synthetic dataset alongside SACRO-ML would have enabled richer insights and earlier identification of improvement opportunities. Looking ahead, providing worked examples, synthetic datasets and example code packages through SACRO-ML would enable TREs to rest and refine an end-to-end ML training, governance and egress more rapidly without the immediate need to recruit external researchers or secure real world use cases. This approach would not only accelerate adoption but also support TREs in building their researcher pipeline while establishing a scalable and well-governed operation model.

9. Conclusions and future direction

The development of the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit and the operational testing of SACRO-ML together establish the EE-SDE's first end-to-end, evidence-based governance pathway for safe, transparent and proportionate machine-learning research. Rather than operating as separate workstreams, these components function as a single, integrated framework: the toolkit provides structured governance, feasibility assessment and risk-based controls, while SACRO-ML delivers the core disclosure-control capability, ante-hoc checks during model development and post-hoc empirical testing at egress, that makes those assessments operational and defensible.

VISTA's testing has demonstrated that evidence-based disclosure control for ML models can be operationalised effectively within a TRE setting. In the EE-SDE demonstrator, researchers maintained familiar modelling workflows while producing standardised artefacts that improved the clarity and reproducibility of airlock review. The challenges observed were primarily operational rather than technical, environment configuration, artefact preparation and early-stage errors common to complex ML pipelines. Performance considerations (e.g., longer runtimes on larger datasets) underline the importance of proportionate, well-designed workflows. Taken together, the combined framework enables the EE-SDE to support a broader range of ML projects with consistent, transparent risk evaluation, while providing output checkers with reproducible, empirical evidence to inform release decisions.

Looking ahead, these processes will continue to evolve. ML methods, assurance expectations and disclosure risks are evolving rapidly, and our governance must evolve with them. We will continue to test future SACRO-ML releases, refine the VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit, and strengthen our local documentation, training materials, onboarding support and interpretive aids so researchers and airlock managers can work confidently and consistently across model types. This will remain aligned with our wider governance pathway to ensure robust disclosure control without creating unnecessary barriers for researchers.

Crucially, we will continue collaborating with DARE UK, SACRO-ML developers and the wider TRE community to extend model coverage, enhance interpretability, and improve process efficiency as new ML techniques emerge and our understanding of privacy risk deepens. Through ongoing shared learning and iterative improvement, we aim to help the UK TRE ecosystem converge on practical, reliable and scalable standards for privacy-preserving model release that deliver public benefit while safeguarding individual privacy.

10. Acknowledgements

The VISTA project was funded as part of DARE UK's Early Adopters, Phase 1 Driver Projects. DARE UK is funded by the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Programme.

The VISTA team comprised the following individuals: Alexis Joannides, Mark Avery, Jack Adamson, Adebambo Ayileka, Tom Billins, Laura Clarke, Onesimus Ekechi, Eleanor Hall, Poojita Karchalkar, Adam Loveday, Elsie Makachiya, Kshitij Nemade, Keiran Raine, Magali Ruffier, Chaitanya Surisetty, Laura Venn and Jacob Wingfield.

The VISTA Team are grateful to DARE UK, the TREvolution team and the other Early Adopters for the opportunity to undertake this work and engage collaboratively in the programme. The project team would also like to express their sincere appreciation to all researchers and public contributors for their valuable insights and constructive engagement throughout the project.

The EE-SDE team would like to thank the SACRO-ML developers, the wider TREvolution community and the researchers who contributed their time to support testing

The authors have no conflict of interest to declare.

11. Glossary

Advantage – Advantage is a metric used in disclosure-risk assessment to quantify how much better an attack performs compared to random guessing. A higher advantage score indicates a greater likelihood that the model may leak sensitive information about individuals in the training data.

Airlock manager - A data security role in Trusted Research Environments, responsible for reviewing and approving data transfers in and out of the TRE.

Ante-hoc / Post-hoc Testing – Testing during model training vs after model training

AUC – Area Under the Curve, refers to the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curve and measures how well a model can distinguish between classes. In the context of disclosure risk, higher AUC values in attack models may indicate a greater ability to infer sensitive information from the trained model.

Checkfile – A checkfile in SACRO-ML is a structured report generated alongside a trained "SafeModel" to summarise disclosure risk checks and model metadata prior to release from a secure environment. It records

key information about the model, including its parameters, safety checks, and an explicit recommendation on whether the model is safe to release.

CPAG – Core Public Advisory Group, the patient and public advisory group established for the Eastern England Secure Data Environment.

CUH – Cambridge University Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust

CUHP – Cambridge University Health Partners, academic health science centre with a mission to improve patient care by uniting the NHS, Industry and Academia

DAC – Data Access Committee, the group of governance, subject matter experts and members of the public who review and make access decisions for a given TRE.

DAR – Data Access Request, the form or document completed by a researcher to describe their research question and data needs so an access decision can be made for a given TRE.

DARE UK – Data and Analytics Research Environments UK, is a programme aimed towards establishing a safe and collaborative network of Trusted Research Environments.

EE-SDE – Eastern England Secure Data Environment, a platform for secure, controlled access to de-personalised patient data for research.

Five Safes – A widely used framework for designing and assessing safe access to sensitive data across five dimensions: Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Settings, Safe Data and Safe Outputs (considered together to achieve “safe use”)

FMAX – Maximum F1-Score, is a performance metric representing the highest F1-score achieved by a membership inference attack across all possible classification thresholds. It is the harmonic mean of Precision (the accuracy of "member" predictions) and Recall (the percentage of total members correctly identified). In privacy auditing, a high FMAX indicates that a model is leaking significant information about its training subjects, while a low FMAX suggests stronger privacy protections.

HIE – Health Innovation East, the innovation arm of the NHS in the East of England.

LIRAAttack – Likelihood Ratio Attack, is a type of membership inference attack that uses likelihood ratios to determine whether a specific data record was included in the training dataset. It compares how likely a model's output is under two scenarios (in-training vs out-of-training). A higher likelihood ratio indicates a greater risk that the model may reveal whether an individual's data was used during training.

ML (Machine Learning) – A set of computational methods that enable systems to learn patterns from data and make predictions or decisions with being explicitly programmed

OMOP – Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model, is a standardised data model used to structure healthcare data in a consistent format across different organisations. It enables researchers to perform analyses using the same definitions, tables, and coding systems (e.g. SNOMED, LOINC), improving reproducibility and comparability of results within secure environments such as the SDE.

PDIF – Probability Difference, measures the difference in prediction probabilities between groups or individuals. In disclosure-risk assessment, it can indicate whether a model behaves differently for specific records, potentially revealing sensitive information.

PDFI – Probability Difference for Individuals, is a more granular measure that evaluates differences in model predictions at an individual level. It is used to assess whether specific individuals may be at higher risk of being identified or inferred from the model outputs.

PPIE – Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement is the active partnership between researchers and the public to shape health research.

SACRO – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs, is a semi-automated system of tools nested in the EE-SDE for checks on research outputs. It can enhance oversight and auditing for airlock managers.

SACRO-ML – Semi-Automated Checking of Research Outputs and ML, includes support for the managing of Statistical Disclosure Control of trained ML models engaged within the Secure Data Environment.

SafeModel – A wrapper around a machine learning model in SACRO-ML that enforces disclosure risk checks and records information needed to assess whether the model is safe to release.

SATRE – Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments, is a community-driven specification for the UK and beyond for building and operating Trusted Research Environments.

SDC – Statistical Disclosure Control, is a set of techniques used by airlock managers, or data custodians more broadly, to prevent the re-identification of individuals or entities in released data.

TRE – Trusted Research Environments, or otherwise Secure Data Environments are highly secure and controlled digital platforms allowing approved researchers access to sensitive, de-identified data for public interest research. These platforms house data and negate the need to move data around.

UKRI - UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) is a non-departmental public body sponsored by the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT).

VISTA – Viable Implementation of SATRE, SACRO and Tools for AI, is the project package aimed towards delivering tools to enhance Statistical Disclosure Checking, support in TREs for ML, and also for establishing a benchmarking standard for Trusted Research Environments.

12. References

1. Eastern Secure Data Environment (EE-SDE) (2026) *Eastern SDE official website*. Available at: <https://easternsde.nhs.uk/>
2. Clarke, L., Nemade, K., Adamson, J., Loveday, A., Venn, L., Hall, E. & Raine, K. (2026) *VISTA AI Risk Assessment Toolkit*. Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19290938>
3. Ritchie, F. (2017) *The “Five Safes”: A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions*. Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.897821>
4. Crespi Boixader, A., Li, S., Liley, J., Ward, L., Cole, C. & Smith, J. (2025) *RELEASE AI: A lifecycle framework for artificial intelligence development and disclosure control in trusted research environments (Version 1.0)*. Preprint. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17159192>

5. Smith, J., Preen, R.J., McCarthy, A., Crespi Boixader, A., Liley, J. & Rogers, S. (2022) *Safe ML model release from Trusted Research Environments: The AISDC package (Version 2)*. arXiv. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2212.0123>
6. Machin, T. et al. (2023) *A standard architecture for Trusted Research Environments*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8411273>
7. Ritchie, F., Tilbrook, A., Green, E., White, P., Derrick, B. & Kendall, C. (2023) *The SACRO guide to statistical output checking*. Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10282525>
8. Jefferson, E. et al. (2022) *GRAIMATTER Green Paper: Recommendations for disclosure control of trained ML models from Trusted Research Environments (TREs)*. Zenodo. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/7089491>
9. Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) (2023) *AI and data protection risk toolkit*. Available at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/artificial-intelligence/guidance-on-ai-and-data-protection/ai-and-data-protection-risk-toolkit/>
10. Amazon Web Services (n.d.) *Synthea synthetic patient generator data in OMOP Common Data Model*. Available at: <https://registry.opendata.aws/synthea-omop> (Accessed: June 2025)
11. Walonoski, J., Kramer, M., Nichols, J., Quina, A., Moesel, C., Hall, D., Duffett, C., Dube, K., Gallagher, T. & McLachlan, S. (2017) *Synthea: An approach, method, and software mechanism for generating synthetic patients and the synthetic electronic health care record*. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 25(3), pp. 230–238. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jamia/ocx079>
12. Nemade, K., Ekechi, O., Karchalkar, P. & Ruffier, M. (2026) *Eastern England SDE Researcher Model Disclosure Control SOP (1.0.0)*. Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19255119>
13. Nemade, K., Ekechi, O., Karchalkar, P. & Magali, R. (2026) *Eastern England Airlock Manager Model Disclosure Control SOP*. Zenodo. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19290204>
14. Office for National Statistics (2026) *Become an accredited researcher*. ONS. Available at: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/aboutus/whatwedo/statistics/requestingstatistics/secureresearchservice/becomeanaccreditedresearcher>
15. Griffiths, E. et al. (2024) *Handbook on Statistical Disclosure Control for Outputs*. ISBN 978 0 906805 039. Available at: <https://securedatagroup.org/guides-and-resources/sdc-handbook/>